

The Holistic Literary Character: *The Body and the Soul* The Holistic Medicine in Literature

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ABSTRACT: Intimacy in fiction is an aesthetical, symbolical and emotional choice. Medicine and novel writing seem to prolong the disease nature has given to mankind. Some writers' propensity for structural themes and motifs from pathology can be considered both a professional and a somatic diagnosis predisposition. Life as a fate leading to death was a general idea at the end of the 19th century. To suddenly utter, that the soul is the body could have destabilised humanistic sciences, and it meant the decentralisation of literary character, the shift of narrative techniques, the conversion of psychology to physiological analysis emphasising the authenticity of sensation. Hortensia Papadat Bengescu's characters are so fleshless, that it's easy to see their soul. Illness is their only connection to the world. Each character tragically aspires to a common life, refused to all of them by their psychological or physiological condition.

KEY WORDS: somatic diagnosis, intimacy, authenticity, character decentralisation, holistic medicine

Psychoanalysis and Aesthetics

The physical aesthetics, the sensorial discourse mostly or completely visual is an archaic type of communication, usually related to narcissism and its avatars or to the concept of body

image. But good is not necessarily beautiful and beautiful is not implicitly good, as Jung pointed out. The ideal of an I-self in which the appearance plays an important role and the ideal I-self featured as a hypertrophic body image can transcribe the most profound suffering. "And this most honest existence, the I-it speaks of the body, and still wants the body, even when it poetizes and raves and flutters with broken wings."¹

When a character talks about his/her physical image, does he/she talk about something else? The body image concept, explained by Schilder (*L'image du corps*, Paris, Gallimard, 1968), and then by Francoise Dolto (*L'image inconsciente du corps*, Paris, Seuil, 1984) has its roots in childhood, when "it includes almost entirely the unconsciousness and it lends itself to all dichotomies: psyche-soma, affect-pulsion, life-death, and consciousness-unconsciousness."² Reality is a conscious option. Does body language express in a metaphorical-symbolical manner a personal silent defence? The more the bodily representation becomes standardised, the more the way a person talks about his/her appearance expressing dissatisfaction for any body part in the mirror, "the body image, crossing every second with the physical type, our existential sub-layer in the world"³ becomes a defensive mechanism against anguish. "The body image as a self image is pulsional, dependent upon the language and updated by transfer;"⁴ hence the inoculation of insecurity and the pathologies of *donjuanism* or *femme-fatale*. In psychoanalysis, beauty and narcissism are not synonymous.

Hortensia Papadat Bengescu's characters cannot free themselves from the tyrannical look into the mirror, this is the essential element filling their solitude and at the same time giving them a sense of autophilia. The tremolo of sensations is conveyed not only to other characters (Lenora, Rin, Lina, Nory) but also to places such as the mansion that "apparently consumed that day in its body the drama of life together with all the beings it had incorporated."⁵ Freud considered narcissism as a common feature of all people, and Jung noted that "whoever goes to himself risks a confrontation with himself. The mirror does not flatter, it faithfully shows whatever looks into it; namely, the face we never show to the world because

we cover it with the persona, the mask of the actor. But the mirror lies behind the mask and shows the true face.”⁶

In Hortensia Papadat Bengescu’s first texts, the mirror is particularly the lonely woman’s accessory, since “the love for me hurts nobody’s heart;”⁷ whether static or made for the lady bag, the mirror is “a magnifying glass meant for autoscopy and a reflector carried through the grey outer events,”⁸ just like in Herta Muller’s text the handkerchief replaces “the person’s acute loneliness”⁹ and it confers the necessary maternal protection (discourse at receiving the Nobel Prize for Literature). Aimée has a Super Ego which she fiercely cultivates. “Aimée’s arrogance came mostly from the belief in her beauty, a belief made stronger in front of the mirror and maintained by the admiration she stirred among her mates at the boarding school. A doll with no character, no expressivity in beauty, but perfect and especially distinct in the material used by mother nature . . . a statuette upon which the eye lingered without impressions, simply annoyed by the immobility of a yet living creature.”¹⁰ Everything she feels is only the tension of her own vexed will, even “that subversive triangle of sensations”¹¹ the Persu sisters have prepared especially for her and the incestuous flirting with Walter, it all seems to be a mandatory repayment of “some kind of carnal compromises taxation.”¹²

Actually, the intimacy subject itself is an auctorial game of mirrors supposed to halve, to be accomplice to yourself or someone else, to free a multiple self (a third Freudian I), a sort of taking into possession in which “the exterior is structured by the interior pattern”¹³ hence the idea of symbolically representing the soul in the shape of a house/place. It’s more difficult nowadays for a writer to successfully keep the distance between inner withdrawal in auto fiction and slipping into para-literature through radical schizoid auctorial forms (in the case of Romain Gary who won twice the Goncourt prize with the novel *La vie devant soi*, under the pseudonym Emile Ajar). Intimacy is an aesthetic symbolic choice full of emotion, and this is the great paradox of its excessive coverage, since the exterior has already been worked upon, relating it to the alterity and adapting it to the scale of unique non-repeatable person, disclaiming “the violence of exteriority, objectivity, truth.”¹⁴

To Hortensia Papadat Bengescu, the aesthetic choice of subjectivity overbidding has been not only a temperamental constancy but also a trick ensuring her credit into the literary man-dominated world, “a passionate disguise,”¹⁵ a physiological problem that she turns over again and again, giving the false impression that “the complete objectivity may result from two subjectivities.”¹⁶

Spiritual Body or Psychoanalytic Interpretation of Literature

After Freud shattered the theories about ego instances in 1933, Merleau-Ponty wrote that “with psychoanalysis, the spirit moves into the body and the other way around, the body moves into the spirit.”¹⁷ “Body am I, and soul—so says the child. And why should one not speak like children?”¹⁸ This seems to be the oldest literary dilemma, periods of continuous castling successively proclaiming one author or another’s supremacy, surprising every time, though they merely restated the same theories. After Nietzsche and Freud in modern times, the New Age theories talked about the almighty spirit, the mental supremacy over physical, and the powerful motivation capable to transform the physical body, the illness and the destiny, even to prolong life; the theories of hypnotic regression that can change the body and its organs, the divination and angels era, somehow bringing back the Oriental theories of levitation and preparing the spirit for immortality, the spiritual era carrying since early days, even *ab nuce*, the stigmata of disease, the astrologers and healers era. The body may not count if one has the right attitude, not ignoring but loving and accepting a shell that plays its own part in strengthening the soul.

The body-sensitivity inadequacy or the quarrel between soul and body, this sub-substance of sensible living carries different names in humanistic sciences: mind-dust, unconsciousness—in psychology, Holy Spirit—in theology, the open core of being—in Buddhism, magnetic flux—in neurobiology. Hortensia Papadat Bengescu’s characters fall ill after they fight anaesthesia of their inner self which eventually claims its rights. They become so fleshless, “the character is transparent, we can see through him or

her without noticing the face,"¹⁹ that one can easily recognize the spiritual body; the world is merely a projection for such characters. "The only reality they are aware of is their soul becoming sensitively physical."²⁰ Seen as "the ultimate frontier of postmodern times, the soul as a projection of codes, socio-cultural patterns and body"²¹ has been sometimes clearly separated from the body, and sometimes identified with it. Antonio R. Damasio, head of Neurology Department of Iowa University, rejects the Darwinian theories in a clinical analysis of corporality, marking that there is no delineation between the flesh and blood body on one hand and "the ethereal soul"²² on the other. The soul, the engine of the ontologically fallen body, the illness as an anticipated sin, "the body that enslaves us and shuts down our reason, and takes into possession life"²³ has been given cultural meaning by Stoicists and this has ultimately lead to a perfect identification of the two components. Damasio, Diogenes Laertios, Epicur, Lucretiu proved to be Naturalists *avant la lettre*, before Descartes gave the first methodical definition of the body and soul dualism, finding the pineal gland as the place where the two meet. This was the birth of the *living body* concept, an anatomical metaphor that has influenced all modern and postmodern phenomenology in humanist science. That meeting point between soul and body in which we want to place our inner self might actually be an empty space, and the literary updating of this junction is in fact the existential crisis which has been an intersection for numerous arts. Following in the footsteps of his master Ortega y Gasset, the psychiatric-phenomenologist Lopez Ibor concludes that "the I-self has an executive disposition"²⁴ and places itself on the trajectory of a necessary fate; Unamuno and Alfred de Vigny have already emphasized this idea.

Throughout the whole Hallipa series, Hortensia Papadat Bengescu seems to reject the solution of harmonization between body and soul, she destroys the material support in all her characters out of a generation neurosis, some sort of social alienation blocks any communication between inner and outer body, particularly any way of living in a unified body where they can hear their intimacy or privacy. The spiritual body, in Papadat Bengescu's novels, corresponds to William James' concept of "mind-dust,"²⁵ also called

continuous consciousness that clinically detects the inner breaches and is clearly opposed to the unconsciousness in psychoanalysis. Even the most intelligent characters, such as Elena Drăgănescu, who attempt to listen to their I-self and harmoniously unite the two coordinates, end up dramatically. Ov. S. Crohmălniceanu has taken over the ingenious Charles Mauron's idea of psychoanalytic interpretation of literature and has consequently overlapped the author's texts in order to find similarities, without "translating into symbols, forcing the profound self to take a definite traceable shape,"²⁶ starting from the notion of *dishevelled maiden* (in novels, old pages of prose and poems in French) that became an emblematic expression used as a title and considered "oxymoronic, since the second term makes the first one ambiguous up to nullification."²⁷ To suddenly utter, in the cultural context after the First World War, that *the soul is the body* could have destabilised the whole area of humanistic sciences, and it meant the decentralisation of literary character, the shift of narrative techniques, the conversion of psychology to physiological analysis emphasising the authenticity of feeling, of sensation, "the evocation through analytical but also sensitive methods."²⁸ Doctor Walter recommends sleeping (reminding of Wagner practicing hydrotherapy for his neurosis), taking care of the person's mood, coquetry and gymnastic, yet the functions of life seem to be more complicated than that. "Neither could she separate the soul from the body, in the same way she couldn't separate that spider web of nervous system from the flesh and the muscle. Still she believed in a different, spiritual body. What kind of body? Around those fibres of the nerves like tentacle, their function was creating a yet impalpable substance which was to be proved real. That substance emanated from sensitivity could take various forms at various living creatures and thus it made an organism."²⁹ After all, we are just a ball of flesh twisted on a spiritual core and death is the only one that ultimately cuts them off.

Interferences between Literature and Medicine

Some writers' propensity for structural themes and motifs from pathology can be considered both a professional and a somatic

diagnosis predisposition. Writing is a somatic technological literary extension of the eyesight; they all complete each other and merge into a new vision of the world, a new “somatoprosepoem.”³⁰ There are numerous examples of medics writers: Augustin Buzura, Vasile Voiculescu, Friedrich Schiller, M. Bulgakov, C. D Zeletin, Bourget, Verga, Lampedusa, Cătălin Vasilescu, Thomas Mann, Tolstoy, Dostoyevsky, and Chekov, who found in suffering a refined source of inspiration for great literature and successfully turned it into fiction. Choosing such a theme doesn’t automatically guarantee a valuable work, since it’s harsh, cruel, repugnant, and also artistically difficult, because it requires a longer incubation period. Blending medicine with literature is the Naturalists’ and Physiologists’ aim; such writers went beyond their field and invaded science, achieving a strangely natural, even monumental unity. The theme is best expressed in Marin Sorescu’s lines: “Doctor, I feel something deadly/Here in the region of my being,/All my organs hurt,/At daytime, my sun hurts,/And at night my moon and my stars hurt,/I feel a pain in the cloud on the sky/That I haven’t even noticed before/And I wake up every morning/With a winter feeling./Uselessly have I taken all sorts of pills,/Have I hated and loved, learned to read/And I have read some books for sure,/Uselessly have I talked to people and thought/Have I been kind, have I been beautiful.../All these haven’t had any effect on me, doctor,/And I’ve wasted so many years on them/I think I’ve fallen ill with death/One day/When I was born.”³¹ We all fall ill, some of us more seriously and dying fast, others more gently and living longer.

Life as a fate leading to death, this is the theme of great writers and critics, Gasset’s and Lopez Ibor’s (in his essay about “penetration of the body into the intimacy field”)³² subject which was intensely discussed last century and already theorized by sociologist and philosopher Julien Freund. It was a general state of mind at the end of the 19th century and beginning of 20th century, “the exhaustion of living, the sickly prostration, the feeling of decay, the sarcastic sadness, the disillusion, the sensuousness of suffering and the grimace of facing reality,”³³ so Papadat Bengescu aligned her works with European writers. Survivor of some intimate catastrophes, she really elaborated pathologies of intimacy “to express the order of a world that lacks its original meaning.”³⁴ Moreover, the Romanian

writer was aware she belonged to a climate which needed a rebirth: "People with Renaissance souls, we all live a life of overstimulation and psychic restlessness amid irritating events. I kind of wait and want the brutality of war as a healing for my frail pains, I prepare my soul to belong to an active nurse who takes care of physical wounds and saves lives, I'm convinced I'm probably more guilty of giving back life than the calamity which shortens it and I see in the passion for charity a way of displaying an unused or unsaturated passion."³⁵ Illness is a specific aspect of life and we all live under its threat with a "natural apprehension;" as long as man is the essence of life and creation, consequently of literature, why should illness be expelled by literary works and artists? Does a work of art stop being artistic just because not everybody likes it? Hortensia Papadat Bengescu herself saw disease as something so inherent to life, that she didn't think she had a preference for it; she simply had medical eyesight, "a spirit that clearly possessed the privilege of seeing."³⁶ "I'd never thought I might have a tendency towards illness, but a natural apprehension . . . it just came to me extemporaneously . . . I confess I have a double curiosity about illness and ill people: a nurse's and a doctor's curiosity, so to speak, because I do not read medical books, or psychological books, I couldn't have the patience to do it. But I do have the patience and the passion for my own investigation, an equal curiosity about the physical and psychic drives . . . Still, illness and ill people was never *the sole* subject of any of my writings . . . To be honest, I look them under the magnifying glass or under the microscope, maybe that's why they seem obsessive."³⁷ The new scientific tendencies in favour of transdisciplinary facets of knowledge, way beyond parallels, influences, patterns, social or cultural functions, show nothing but the interaction between various medical fields, recently interpreted from the New Age point of view, bringing spirituality and psychology to the fore (Dumitru Constantin Dulcan, Serghei Lazarev, Brian Weiss, Dan Mirahorian, Valeriu Popa, Anatol Basarab, Louise Hay, Doreen Virtue) both in diagnosis and causes, since illness is seen as "a pre-ordered way of self-destruction;"³⁸ "I'm an emotional person. But when I write, I cannot favour any of my characters; I cannot favour either life or death, because a ruthless sense of reality, a terrible weakness of

seeing reality just the way it is takes away my subjectivity. World and life remain organs on my dissection table.”³⁹ Cognitivism and neurosciences say that perception and expression of reality depend on the structure and patterns in human brains, “extension and nexus of a new body surpassing pure animalism.”⁴⁰ Exploring the body is a merciless, surgical act, accordingly to Foucault’s episteme of man: man = body + solitude, the body can be seen and touched but the solitude is universal and common to everybody. The limit and the pointer of ontological solitude in postmodern society is love itself, an unsacred, invented, pure biological love, a body inferno.

Thanks to Hortensia Papadat Bengescu’s works, the Romanian literature gained the richest medical vocabulary, the physiologic man is shown with a rather technical skill, from a biologist’s and a clinician’s point of view, acknowledging that any suffering of the body is mainly a suffering of the soul. This clinical study of various illnesses is a critical *no*, all these individual disorders reflect the social disruptions since we carry deep within our subconsciousness the endowment of the whole human beings. “Every person is a spiritual history of the world”⁴¹ or, as Blaga said in a poem, “in the nameless country every human being will have to start/learning once again/the forgotten stories of the blood./Man is nothing but the measure/of a complete journey.”⁴²

The last novel of the series, *The Stranger*, is a proof of “the most severe pathology, the history pathology.”⁴³ Magdalena Popescu saw in this novel a virgin and rich source for the psychoanalytical criticism, while G. Călinescu marked that “an ill creature arise interest for clinicians only.” Whatever the critics say, there’s no question that nobody has ever seized in a more subtle and comprehensive way the state of illness, in a world doomed to perish by all physical, social, moral, aesthetical meanings. The characters’ lineage doesn’t go further than two generations, and according to the cyclical rules, after the extinction comes a superior new level, why not the life after death, much better than anything they’ve lived and tried in the narrated life, as Kahlil Gibran’s prophet says: “You would know the secret of death. But how shall you find it unless you seek it in the heart of life? . . . If you would indeed behold the spirit of death, open your heart wide unto the body of life. For life and death is one,

even as the river and the sea are one . . . and when the earth shall claim your limbs, then shall you truly dance.”⁴⁴

In many novels the hero is usually punished in the end by illness or death, but the novels of this series start with illness and, in an “imitative polyphony of a dominating leitmotif endlessly proliferating,”⁴⁵ with every breaking up of a couple, they inevitably go to the downfall of a whole generation, not as pain or punishment but as release, in Edgar Allan Poe’s words “the crisis . . ./And the fever called Living/Is conquered at last.”⁴⁶ One doesn’t pity them and isn’t afraid of becoming tainted, but rather relieved. If birth is a pain for two, shared between mother and newborn, death is a pain for only one, anyone. In front of death we all stand alone, empty handed. We simply surrender. When we come into the world our fists are tight, expressing the will to live, to fight for victory, and then when we die we open our hands expressing surrender and showing the others we carry nothing out of this world. Waiting for the death to come in a conscious manner is a terrifying experience, so the death is ultimately a release. “We are ourselves both in winning and in dying.”⁴⁷ Blaga thought that talking about death is talking about life, beauty, rising high, flying, about the invisible thread that bonds man to God. Thinking about death is enjoying the gift of life, not waiting in sorrow for the death to come and take you away. Only around death you find the true measure of life. Those lying in hospital beds are no longer frightened, they long for death. Suffering is the wisest and the hardest teacher, it opens our eyes to the most unsuspected paths, “through pain the sky and earth separate themselves in us.”⁴⁸

The unsettled war between masculine and feminine, between master and slave turns into the fight between desire and hatred, life and death, author and character. “In order to continue living after he saved himself through his character, the author has to sacrifice the character.”⁴⁹ Art is, according to Buddha, the safest madness on the way to salvation, and according to Goethe “the safest way to break ourselves from the world and yet the safest way to tighten ourselves to it.”⁵⁰ To those who do not like this theme and refuse to think like children do, that “body am I, and soul,” Nietzsche answers in *Thus Spoken Zarathustra: a Book for All and None*: “To the despisers of the body I want to speak. I would not have them learn and teach

differently, but merely say farewell to their own bodies—and thus become silent.”⁵¹ The work of art is not to be confused with the aesthetical value, it includes, it stores different forms of aesthetical value and only one of them can assure the entire artistic value of the work. The work of art is an asset; the aesthetical phenomenon is a value. “Being a product of the human spirit, the work of art is closely related to the creative act, it can never detach itself totally from the creative process, between artist and his work there’s an organic relationship, full of consequences for the total understanding of the work.”⁵² On the other hand, Ion Caraion distinguishes the literature–aesthetics–life trinity which gives back the writer his old status. “Besides the shaded supple fragile attributes of literature, under the multicoloured intelligent hat of aesthetics there come to sit now the virile bristled harsh intense attributes of life.”⁵³ The writer has to sketch an abstract drawing out of the memories he kept in his skin, an intensive drawing made up of the impressions of mingled bodies, invisible sensual tattoos. Literature has discovered the soul of this surface. Writing and expressing are inseparable from the body. “The text is contaminated by the body.”⁵⁴

Hortensia Papadat Bengescu is defined by this type of writing, the way she chose to write is a kind of *trade mark* seemingly anticipating the linguistic theories about the dissolution of the language. “The letter is dead, the body is alive. As I like to say, the word comes to life only after it is given a body. When I say word, I actually mean sense. Well, this sense has to spring out of your flesh, your somatic sensitivity.”⁵⁵

The Anamnesis of Body and Soul Illnesses. The Pathological as Narrative Art (Pathology with Medical Record/Hidden Pathology)

Reflecting upon diary as taciturn writing, Eugen Simion agreed that an ugly person is also mean, but he went further combining these two features with stupidity: “What face does stupidity combined with malice have? Not a bright face.”⁵⁶ These reflections have their roots in the antic Greek tradition, which held in honour

the correlation between appearance and soul. In the 19th century the German philosopher Lavatter came back to the physiognomic doctrine, influencing the writings of Balzac and even Dostoyevsky. The attempt to derive human nature out of the physiognomy and the certitude that an ugly person can only be mean just like a beautiful person can only be good, have gone a long way and they are easy to recognise in Papadat Bengescu's texts.

How could the Hallipa series be bright if it has darkened the author's face? Throughout the pages of the novels the malice goes hand in hand with ugliness, inner and outer deformity, depicting monsters or giants who cause nothing but pain and show nothing but ignorance, "l'homme-enfant, un parfait imbécile, un automate, une statue immobile et presque insensible."⁵⁷ Everything is normal here as far as it is pathological, and the degradation by illness and death, though seen as a superior sensuousness, is socially experienced, reminding of Thomas Mann's *Magic Mountain*. This paradox is explained by Michael Riffaterre as a reversal between semantic semes, between the comparison terms, that ends up eliminating the differences and a "similitude in identity;"⁵⁸ the imitation becomes the main referent and the natural comes out of discussion "by being replaced with the artificial, since the Decadentism produces a subversive comment of an interpretation it deconstructs using a second grade referent, a copy."⁵⁹ Because not every human character is illustrative of the society, the writer was forced to resort to certain individual types. Even the unconsciousness has a historical feature, due to the fact that every person takes over the whole psychic structure of the ancestors. "What comes to us from outside, and, for that matter, *everything* that rises up from *within*, can only be *our own* if we are capable of inner amplitude equal to that of the incoming content. Real increase of personality means consciousness of an enlargement that flows from inner sources. Without psychic depth we can never be adequately related to the magnitude of our object. It has therefore been said quite truly that a man grows with the greatness of his task. But he must have within himself the capacity to grow; otherwise even the most difficult task is of no benefit to him. More likely he will be shattered by it."⁶⁰

Should it be only by accident that we meet, sometimes over hundreds of pages, not a single positive character? They are representative of this fake *haut-société*, eager whether to gain or to maintain their social status, and therefore it was necessary that the inner individual drives to be adequate to the social mechanism, in other words to be a perfect congruity between the internal and the external biography. “The individuals’ fate can no longer be separated, from various points of view, from the fate of the category and the group they belong to and they project themselves further on the historical canvas depending on these relations”⁶¹ Somehow rebellious, Vladimir Streinu called these writers quakers, using the English term for the religious society of friends, taken from the spinning dervishes and all sorts of mystics in trance. So, after pathetically confronting life, death, fate, nation, God, “livid with fear, they experience the existential happiness of morally convulsing, and they tend to impose to our entire culture the twisted formula of their soul . . . these formulae with a strict individual and even biological content have vulgarized philosophy making it handy. Could this style of desperation, of dry suffering, be the disease of our century? Where did these quakers come from, sparing our Church but invading our Culture?”⁶² And when a “complete study of health dissonance”⁶³ adds to all these, the man being looked upon as a succession of interdependent physiological and psychological phenomena, it’s more than obvious that the author is a legitimate spokesperson of her time, as Mircea Zăciu notices: “The process of bourgeoisie disintegration, under all its pathological aspects, has found in this female writer a lucid, then ironic, then sarcastic interpreter who is no stranger to the human suffering side of a tragic impossible aspiration towards the purity Johann Sebastian Bach’s music symbolizes.”⁶⁴ One step from the grotesque, the writer doesn’t reach the Naturalists caricature, but “a tragi-comic both horrible and humorous.”⁶⁵

Papadat Bengescu’s propensity for pathological study, that Călinescu talked about, can be explained by Naturalism influence, since “pathology suited very well the mechanical determinism that the school of Médan saw in life.”⁶⁶ Physiology always leaves a psychological mark. Disease is never the same, never simple, never cured, reason of fears and self-analyses. Disease and its psychology

seem to be mainly related to “the crazy state of mind in the world;”⁶⁷ otherwise, the characters refuse to understand that “everything that’s on the plate/has to be lived.”⁶⁸

A woman, Hortensia Papadat Bengescu, records all the physiological misery of some bodies crying out for help. Most often, the fragile nervous system is the one that suffers, the neuron being the only cell not able to regenerate. One can seize the interest for what remains unexpressed, for the will that doesn’t come into act and its repression can establish a biography. One of the artistic accomplishments the writer uses to make the mentally ill person a drama character is repression, his/her illness, however easy to be recognized, doesn’t eventually get any name, because anyway “the moral disorder and degeneration go hand in hand and mingle.”⁶⁹ With her *stirring* style, Hortensia Papadat Bengescu sort of affiliates herself to the Naturalist writers who make a physiological art that “doesn’t step back in front of indecency or humiliation or the most shameless rudeness.”⁷⁰ The Naturalism came into the literary scene when the writers tried to compete with the scientist, invading the hospitals with the pen in their hands and recording the detail, sure that they were making educational work. The pathological conditions are Hortensia Papadat Bengescu’s favourite field too but, unlike Naturalists, in her texts the body is revealed through soul, and these motifs are inseparable, nobody else until her has ever insisted so much upon these two and related the physiology and psychology to the social life. After Freud elaborated the principles of psychoanalyse, the interest for the hidden life of soul has become common and has been proudly accepted by the writers, as another proof of “how serious the novelist’s work is.”⁷¹ So, to make science in a novel comes to be a real literary merit. Proust said that medicine is the one that prolongs the disease nature has given us. Perpessicius adds: medicine *and novel*, talking about the clinical applicability and likely in Papadat Bengescu’s novels.

We often hear that the writer has to avoid the contact with psychiatry and leave to the medics the descriptions of psychical states. In reality, no writer has taken this into account and it was impossible to do so because a writer’s main mission is to describe the universe within so that, one way or another, the writers have

always been predecessors of science. More so the border between the normal and the so called ill psychic is, first of all, a conventional delimitation, and, secondly, so instable that each of us can cross over it several times during the day. On the other hand, psychiatry is concerned not only about illnesses (understandable solely in relation to healthy state), but also about merely disorders. That way, the writer cannot avoid the psychiatrist and the psychiatrist cannot avoid the writer, and the literary approach of a psychiatric theme cannot harm the aesthetic value. Georges Dumas said that “the real master of the psychiatrist is the novelist.”⁷²

Referring to the hidden pathologies study, Perpessicius places their literary approach in front of psychiatry: “Either there’s a case of perhaps innocent hysteria, favoured by certain disorders and as a consequence of sexual shyness, or there’s a case of intellectual obnubilation, where the dysmnesia of evoking is accompanied by a complex of symptoms, whatever the psychiatry may say, how many diagnoses it may make, how many conclusions and analyses it may draw, nothing makes it equal to the novel of this case, that only Mrs. Hortensia Papadat Bengescu could make up of so many hidden fibres and so much weightlessness, well-rounded and human.”⁷³ These words synthesize in the best way the theme of the novels. The medical record makes way for the real characters of the book: *the anomalies* of any kind, a catalogue of absurdities that ends up with the transformed character living in a mechanical, sleepy, paralysed state, a mechanical reduction of the human being typical for the Naturalist literature. The diminished mobility of mind and body depicted by the novelist gives life to “the monumentality and the mystery of nature itself.”⁷⁴

Ovid. S. Crohmălniceanu yet thought one *can* live among these people who are able to show in distress “the slice of humanity within them.”⁷⁵ Each character tragically aspires, in his/her own way, to a common life, refused to all of them by their psychological or physiological condition. So, in Hortensia Papadat Bengescu’s work, there are a hidden pathology and a medical recording pathology, two groups that gathers all the characters of the Hallipa series. Papadat Bengescu’s human being is defined by a social universe. The Hallipa, the Drăgănescu and the Valter families climbed but also crawled

their way on the social scale and end up with deep scratches, in Ovid. S. Crohmălniceanu's words. Their attempt to dominate this social universe results in a psychical falsification, and illness is nothing else than "the solution" the author found to "restore" the frustrated personality on the conscious way to death. Nory, one of the characters, actually spreads the idea of a class privilege of suffering. Is the disease a restoration? Yes, in the sense that only through disease man eludes the striving of defending his social status, that has taken all his power, and the spirit is "the life that cuts out right in the flesh of life."⁷⁶ Conventions, obligations, everything is dissolved in the miracle and "the nobility" of illness. Towards the universe the illness reveals, the man is ultimately freed. Liberty or the illusion of liberty can only be gained by escaping the metaphysical. There's a double escaping, hence two kinds of illnesses and ill characters: some of them are "luckier" and completely free themselves from universe (incurable disease such as Maxentiu's phthisis), while the others are ill as a sign of weakness, of psychical disablement to bear the social constraint, and this is a pathetic way of being free (Lenora, Drăgănescu find their shelter in Walter's hospital). They are the only one to share the human feelings of self-pity. Accordingly to Emil Cioran, man has three lives: intrauterine (unconscious), extrauterine (conscious) and postmortem (afterlife), and without the last one it would all be foolish and meaningless. At birth, the soul comes not in order to be happy, but to serve its time, because happiness is to be found up there, around the divine being, and no experience on earth can compare to that. Man "comes with a certain purpose in this world, he comes to take his dose of bitterness and sadness, to change something at mankind."⁷⁷

When the author questioned about the ways to make her characters free and searched a solution to restore them, choosing illness as an answer is really tragic because, on its conscious way to death, illness cannot be a solution, it is nothing more than "a vague mysticism of moral purgation through suffering."⁷⁸ There's no escaping even with doctor's help. The few chameleonic recoveries (actually, the agonies before dying) the ill character has are due to his own psyche making a last effort. Medics are, in the Hallipa series, "the most seriously ill characters the author has imagined."⁷⁹ Either

impostors in practicing medicine (dr. Rim, the twin bacteriologists Hallipa, professor G.), or eminent clinicians in a field which is by excellence ambiguous, that is psychiatry (dr. Walter and Cojan), or with a clear specialization (dr. Răut—TBC. and dr. Caro—infectious diseases), they perform their own healing. Some of them solve their inferiority complexes (Rim and Caro), others—their frustrations. That’s why the most serious illnesses are analysed relatively independent from the curative medicine and closely dependent on psychology, and their concern for the disease gives a sense to their lives, saves them from the existential dissatisfaction. True death is not rottenness but repulsion to life, indifference to feelings. “Man is forced to struggle with the daily death of his body in order to transcend it.”⁸⁰ That’s why people’s death is different from animals’, and only the most unlucky people die like dogs, not like humans.

NOTES

¹ Friedrich Nietzsche, *Thus Spoken Zarathustra: a Book for All and None*, trad. Șt. Aug. Doinaș (București: Editura Humanitas, 1994), 90.

² Gisele Harrus Revidi, *Psihologia simțurilor*, trad. Nicolae Baltă, (București: Editura Trei, 2008), 104.

³ Cf. F Dolto; see Revidi, 105.

⁴ Ibid, 107.

⁵ Hortensia Papadat Bengescu, *Fecioarele despletite*, ediție. îngrijită de Gheorghe Radu, prefață de Eugenia Tudor (București: Editura Pentru Literatură, 1966), 154.

⁶ C. G. Jung, *Collective Works 1. The Archetypes and the Collective Unconscious—Opere complete 1. Arhetipurile și inconștientul colectiv* (București: Editura Trei, 2003), 29.

⁷ Mihaela Stanciu Vraja, *Hortensia Papadat Bengescu în oglinda prozei de tinerețe* (București: Editura Pro Universitaria, 2015), 127.

⁸ Corina Ciocârlie, *Femei în fața oglinzii* (Cluj–Napoca: Editura Echinoc, 1998), 28.

⁹ *Caiet. Herta Muller la București*, 27–28 sept. 2010 (București: Editura Humanitas Fiction & Centrul de carte germană, 2010), 5–20.

¹⁰ Hortensia Papadat Bengescu, *Opere*, Academia Română, Fundația Națională pentru Știință și Artă; ediție, note și comentarii de Gabriela Omăt; studiu introductiv de Eugen Simion (București: Academia Română, 2012), 864.

¹¹ Ibid, 1029.

¹² Ibid, 1033.

¹³ Gaston Bachelard, *La poetique de l'espace*, Presse Universitaire de France, Paris, 2007, p. 23;

¹⁴ Jean Baudrillard, "La sphere enchantee de l'intime," in *Autrement* (nr. 81, 1986): 15.

¹⁵ T. Vianu, "Hortensia Papadat Bengescu," in *Sburătorul* (an II, nr. 23, 30 oct. 1920); also in *Scriitori români ai sec. XX* (București: Editura Minerva, 1979), 216.

¹⁶ Simona Sora, *Regăsirea intimității* (București: Editura Cartea Românească, 2008), 89.

¹⁷ M. Merleau-Ponty, *Signes* (Paris: Gallimard, 2001), 290 as quoted by Sora, *Regăsirea intimității*, 82.

¹⁸ Friedrich Nietzsche, *Thus Spoken Zarathustra*, 89

¹⁹ Dana Dumitriu, *Ambasadorii sau despre realismul psihologic* (București: Editura Cartea Românească, 1976), 194–195.

²⁰ Nicolae Manolescu, *Arca lui Noe*, vol. II (București: Editura Minerva, 1981), 11.

²¹ Andrei Bodi, Georgeta Moarcăș, *Trupul și litera. Explorări critice în biografia și opera lui Gh. Crăciun* (Cluj-Napoca: Editura Casa Cărții de Știință, 2012), 57.

²² Antonio R Damasio, *Eroarea lui Descartes. Emoțiile și creierul uman*, trad. Irina Tănăsescu (București: Editura Humanitas, 2004), as quoted by Sora, *Regăsirea intimității*, 44.

²³ Marc Richir, *Le corps. Essai sur l'interiorite*, Optiques Philosophie (Paris: Hatier, 1993), 44.

²⁴ Juan Jose Lopez Ibor, *El descubrimiento de la intimidad y otros ensayos*, Coleccion Austral (Madrid: Espasa-Calpe, 1952), 38.

²⁵ William James, *The Principles of Psychology*, (Cambridge: Harvard University Press, 1981), as quoted by Sora, *Regăsirea intimității*, 93.

²⁶ Ovidiu S. Crohmălniceanu, *Cinci prozatori în cinci feluri de lectură* (București: Cartea Românească, 1984), 160.

²⁷ Elena Zaharia Filipaș, *Studii de literatură feminină* (București: Paideia, 2004), 44.

²⁸ Tudor Vianu, *Arta prozatorilor români*, vol II (București: Editura pentru literatură, 1966), 209.

²⁹ Hortensia Papadat Bengescu, *Fecioarele despletite*, pref. Eugenia Tudor (București: Editura pt. Lit., 1966), 188.

³⁰ Gheorghe Crăciun, "Mircea Nedelciu și curtea interioară a literaturii. Corpuri netransparente, sociografii narative, tratamente ambulatorii, in Pactul somatografic," in *Observator Cultural* (nr. 133): 74.

³¹ Marin Sorescu *apud* Maria Bâgiu Marino, *Oameni și oameni* (Brașov: SC Imp SA, 2003), 24.

³² Juan Jose Lopez Ibor, *El descubrimiento de la intimidad y otros ensayos*, Coleccion Austral (Madrid: Espasa-Calpe, 1952), 38, as quoted by Sora, *Regăsirea intimității*, 18.

³³ Carmen Georgeta Ardelean, *Hortensia Papadat Bengescu „marea europeană” a literaturii române. Pledoarii* (Cluj-Napoca: Editura Eikon, 2013), 42.

³⁴ Sora, *Regăsirea intimității*, 34.

³⁵ Hortensia Papadat Bengescu, *Scrisori către Ibrăileanu*, scrisoare din 10 iulie 1916, ediție îngrijită de M. Bordeianu, Gr. Botez, I. Lăzărescu, Dan Mănuță și Al. Teodorescu (București: EPL, 1966), 52.

³⁶ Viola Vancea, *Hortensia Papadat Bengescu: universul citadin repere și interpretări* (București: Editura Eminescu, 1980), 40.

³⁷ Dan Petrașincu, “Cu scriitoarea Hortensia Papadat Bengescu despre romanul Logodnicul și despre creație,” in *Vremea* (anul VIII, nr. 389, 26 mai 1935): 9; reprinted in Dan Petrașincu, *Romanul românesc în interviuri*, (București: Editura Minerva, 1984), 639–640.

³⁸ Carmen Georgeta Ardelean, *Hortensia Papadat*, 42.

³⁹ “Cu scriitoarea Hortensia Papadat Bengescu despre romanul Logodnicul și despre creație,” in *Vremea* (anul VIII, nr. 389, 26 mai 1935): 9; reprinted in Dan Petrașincu, *Romanul românesc în interviuri*, (București: Editura Minerva, 1984), 636–637.

⁴⁰ Alexandru Mușina, *Șase cuvinte cheie pentru proza lui Gh. Crăciun in Trupul și litera* (Cluj–Napoca: Casa Cărții de Știință, 2012), 53.

⁴¹ Marino, *Oameni și oameni*, 49.

⁴² Ibid.

⁴³ Andreia Roman, *Hortensia Papadat Bengescu–Vocația și stilurile modernității* (Pitești: Editura Paralela 45, 2007), 108.

⁴⁴ Marino, *Oameni și oameni*, 345.

⁴⁵ Ardelean, *Hortensia Papadat Bengescu*, 105.

⁴⁶ Marino, *Oameni și oameni*, 122.

⁴⁷ Ibid., 126.

⁴⁸ Ibid., 313.

⁴⁹ Liliana Truță, *Aspecte ale androginiei textuale la Gh. Crăciun*, in *Trupul și litera*, ed.cit., p. 116;

⁵⁰ Thomas Mann, *Pătimirile și măreția lui Richard Wagner*, trad. Alexandru David, (București: Editura Humanitas, 2013), 44.

⁵¹ Nietzsche, *Thus Spoken Zarathustra*, 89.

⁵² Cf. an article authored by Victor Iancu and published in *Preocupări literare*, an VII, nr 8–9, august–septembrie 1942): 458–466; as quoted by George Ivașcu, *Cumpăna cuvântului 1939–1945. Mărturii ale conștiinței românești în anii celui de-al doilea război mondial*, (București: Editura Eminescu, 1977), 322–323.

⁵³ Ion Caraion, “Războiul artei,” in *Orizont* (an I, nr. 6, 1 februarie 1945): 5, in Ivașcu, *Cumpăna cuvântului*, 549.

⁵⁴ Cezar Gheorghe, “Intersecțiile literaturii cu filosofia în opera lui Gheorghe Crăciun” in *Trupul și Litera. Explorări critice în biografia și opera lui Gheorghe Crăciun*, eds. Andrei Bodiu și Georgeta Moarcăs (Cluj–Napoca: Editura Cărții de Știință, 2013), 215.

⁵⁵ Gheorghe Crăciun, *În căutarea referinței*, (Pitești: Editura Paralela 45, Colecția 80, Seria Eseuri, 1998), 242.

⁵⁶ Eugen Simion, *Fragmente critice I* (București: Editura Grai și suflet, 1998), 280.

⁵⁷ Jean Jacques Rousseau in Radu Petrescu, *Meteorologia Lecturii*, (București: Editura Cartea Românească, 1982), 150.

⁵⁸ Michael Riffaterre, *Decadent Paradoxe*, in *Perennial Decay: On the Aesthetics and Politics of Decadence*, p. 66, in Angelo Mitcheivici, *Decadență și decadentism*, (București: Editura Curtea Veche, 2011), 56.

⁵⁹ Oscar Wilde, discourse *The Decay of Lying–Decăderea minciunii*, traducere și note Magda Teodorescu, prefață de Mircea Mihăieș (Iași: Polirom, 2001) in Angelo Mitcheivici, *op.cit.*, p. 57;

⁶⁰ Jung, *Opere Complete 1*, 128.

⁶¹ Marin Manu Bădescu, *De la Nicolae Filimon la Marin Preda* (Pitești: Editura Zodia Fecioarei, 1998), 99.

⁶² Cf. Vladimir Streinu's article in *Preocupări literare* (VII, 8–9, aug–sep 1942): 417–421, as quoted by Ivașcu, *Cumpăna cuvântului*, 328.

⁶³ Liviu Petrescu, *Realitate și romanesc* (București: Editura Tineretului, 1965), 96.

⁶⁴ Mircea Zăciu, *Masca Geniului* (București: E.P.L., 1967), 198.

⁶⁵ Ion Bogdan Lefter, *Scurtă istorie a romanului românesc* (Pitești: Editura Paralela 45, 2001), 50.

⁶⁶ Ovid. S. Crohmălniceanu, *Literatura română între cele două războaie mondiale*, vol I (București: E. P. L, 1967), 445.

⁶⁷ Mircea Nedelciu, *Zodia scafandrului* (București: Compania, 2000), 60–61.

⁶⁸ Mircea Nedelciu, *Proză scurtă: Aventuri într-o curte interioară* (București, Compania, 2003), 19.

⁶⁹ Constantin Ciopraga, *Hortensia Papadat–Bengescu* (București: Editura Cartea Românească, 1973), 155.

⁷⁰ George Călinescu, *Cronicile optimistului* (București: E. P. L, 1964), 143–144.

⁷¹ Mihai Zamfir, *Cealaltă față a prozei* (București: Editura Eminescu, 1988), 25.

⁷² Nicolae Manolescu, *Arca lui Noe* (București: Editura 100+1 Gramar, 2000), 181.

⁷³ P. Perpessicius, *Scriitori români*, vol. III (București: Editura Minerva, 1989), 284.

⁷⁴ Radu Petrescu, *Meteorologia Lecturii* (București: Editura Cartea Românească, 1982), 148.

⁷⁵ Crohmălniceanu, *Literatura română*, 449.

⁷⁶ Nietzsche, *Thus Spoken Zarathustra*, 315.

⁷⁷ Marino, *Oameni și oameni*, 272.

⁷⁸ Ibid.

⁷⁹ Roxana Sorescu, *Interpretări* (București: Editura Cartea Românească, 1979), 208.

⁸⁰ Marino, *Oameni și oameni*, 70.